

HadCET v2.1.1.0

Release Notes, March 2026

Overview

The **v2.1.1.0** release is an incremental update to the HadCET V2 temperature series. This update extends the version-controlled dataset to include quality-controlled station observations for the calendar year 2025.

The incorporation of quality-controlled 2025 observations into the version-controlled dataset does not alter the previously published v2.1.0.0 + Provisional series values. No amendments to earlier data are required.

- Version-controlled dataset available via [CEDA](#) (extended to 2025)
- Version-controlled + Provisional dataset available via Met Office Hadley Centre observations datasets [webpage](#)